

Nanoparticles Applications: For Environmental Friendliness, And Cost Effectiveness, Sustainable Agriculture

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Abstract:

Food security has become a critical concern in globe due to the rise in human population and the current climate change crisis. Usage of conventional agrochemicals to maximize crop yields has resulted in the degradation of fertile soil, environmental pollution as well as human and agro ecosystem health risks. Due to use of different chemical fertilizers, pesticides and, other agrochemicals products for increasing crop yield have adverse effect on biodiversity, soil fertility, and in turn on the ecosystems. Recently, nanoparticles have been recognized as potential fertilizers with properties that make them more absorbable and readily available for plant use than their bulk counterpart. Nanoparticles are gaining a reputation in the field of agriculture for the remediation of soil degradation in a sustainable way. The application of nanoscaled nutrient elements such as silver, zinc, copper, iron, titanium, magnesium and calcium as fertilizers and utilizing green synthesized nanomaterials as one of the ways to palliate the use of environmentally toxic chemicals in the cropping system and discusses the various benefits of nanoparticles, ranging from plant growth stimulation to defence against pathogens.

Nanoparticles (NPs) due to their compact size, ease of transport, ease of handling, long shelf life, and high efficiency make it the preferred choice of farmers over other conventional products. In depth, it delts with negative and positive impact of nanoparticles on different crops, water treatment for irrigation purposes, nanocarriers and fertilizers, nanoparticles for plant protection Nanoinsecticides, Nanopesticides, Nanofungicides, Nanoherbicides, Nanobactericides, Nanosensors, slow or controlled release fertilizers, clay nanotubes and Nanobarcodes have been applied in multiplexed bioassays and general encoding in biological and nonbiological applications.

Keywords: Agriculture; Nanoparticles; Nanofertilizers; Plant Growth.

Introduction:

Nanotechnology is defined as the scientific knowledge to manipulate and control matter in the nanoscaled range to make use of size- and structure-dependent properties and phenomena distinct from those at smaller or larger scales (Roco, M.C, 2011). The use of nanomaterials dates from 4500 years ago. In some civilizations, nanofibers were used for the reinforcement of ceramic matrixes. In addition,

the ancient Egyptians of the third century used NMs for the production of different forms of dyes (Jeevanandam *et. al.* 2018). The development of nanotechnology has resulted in the production of nanoparticles with many applications in different fields, such as the food industry, medicine and textiles (Luksiene, 2017).

In agriculture, their usage as fertilizers and pesticides has been reported in many studies. Elements such as silver, zinc, copper, iron,

silicon, titanium, magnesium, and manganese have been supplied to plants in different forms, hence, having a beneficial effect on their growth and yield as they fight against infections and act as fertilizers or carriers of nutrients (Rastogi *et.al.*2019) Although scientific reports have demonstrated the applications of Nanofertilizers and nanoparticles in crop nutrition and pest control, the adoption of this sustainable alternative is still in its infancy. Hence, this review, therefore, aims to provide insights into the broad agricultural applications of nanoparticles as Nanofertilizers.

The usage of living structures in nanoparticles production is a real alternative to physical and chemical processes owing to its environmental friendliness and cost-effectiveness. Biosynthesis of nanoparticles using plants has been demonstrated to be green chemistry that interconnects plant sciences with nanotechnology and helps achieve the synthesis of nanoparticles at room temperature, neutral pH and a low cost without the use of environmentally harmful chemicals (Parveen *et. al.* 2016). Plants and their by-products have demonstrated essential properties in the synthesis process of nanoparticles as their usage is more beneficial than other systems (Siddiqui *et.al.*2015).

They are increasingly being used because they facilitate the development of nanoparticles and increase the success rate of synthesis, as researchers strive to build upscaled processes of mono dispersed and stable nanoparticles (Iravani,*et.al.*2015). The conventional approach for making metallic nanoparticles from plants employs a reducing agent derived from dried plant biomass and a metallic salt as a precursor.

Biomolecules such as phenolics, alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, enzymes and proteins have been reported to be involved in the synthesis reaction (Ovais *et.al.* 2018). Hence, it

has been reported that the hydroxyl groups present in carbohydrates, amino acids, proteins and nucleic acids of plants act in the stabilization of ENPs (Dorjnamjin *et.al.* 2008). Green synthesis of nanoparticles is becoming a very insightful topic nowadays. There is rising attention to the use of organisms. The biological production of metallic and metal oxide nanoparticles is less harmful to the environment than the current chemical or physical approaches.

Plants have shown a large interest in expanding the biosynthesis of nanoparticles on a large scale as the plant-mediated nanoparticles are very stable and have diverse sizes and shapes compared to the ones produced through other biological systems (Ramesh *et.al.*2014). Synthesized nanoparticles can be carbon-based or metal-based. The most produced and used metal-based engineered nanoparticles are zinc oxide (ZnO), titanium dioxide (TiO₂), gold (Au), silver (Ag), cerium oxide (CeO₂) and copper oxide (CuO) or dioxide (Cu₂O) nanoparticles. Other nanoparticles, such as Mn, Fe₃O₄, CuO, CaO and Fe₃O₄, are also widely used and produced (Rico *et.al.*2015).

To maximize yields and alleviate poverty and malnutrition, nanoparticles have been recognized as highly beneficial for plant biomass production and enhancement of crop nutritional quality. This review highlighted the attributes of biosynthesized nanomaterials as sustainable alternatives to conventional chemical fertilizers. These potential agro-inputs can be readily absorbed by plants and are environmentally friendly crop nutrient supplements (Ca, Mg and Fe NPs), with advantages beyond fertilization. The use of nanoparticles, such as Ti, Ag and Zn, which can be integrated into cropping systems to enhance the plant's defence mechanism, against disease attack. However, fewer studies have investigated the broad application of

nanoparticles in pest and disease management, offering an opportunity for future research in crop protection.

Although the application of nanoparticles has been revolutionary for crop productivity, the response of plant-associated microorganisms to nano-based amendments remains unclear. Similarly to bulk chemical fertilizers or pesticides, nano-based agricultural amendments may have an impact on plant-associated microorganisms. Exposure of plant-associated microorganisms to nanoparticles can either be beneficial or harmful depending on various factors. Hence, further investigation on the interaction and response of plant-associated microorganisms to nanoparticles is warranted to ensure sustainable precision agricultural practices. Microorganisms are extremely important for overall soil and plant health (Goswami *et al.*, 2016). Diverse genera of microorganisms have been identified in soils and crops, and they play an important role in the regulation of agro ecosystem productivity, soil physicochemical characteristics, and plant health (Dinca *et al.*, 2022).

A vast majority of plant-associated microorganisms are found in the soil, near plant roots in the region called the rhizosphere, where they serve essential ecological functions such as promoting plant growth (Bello-Akinosho *et al.*, 2021). Although plants associated microorganisms can exert both negative and positive impacts on the host plants, the focus of this review is majorly on the impact on beneficial plant associated microorganisms.

Previous research in plant microbe interactions has laid the foundation by describing certain factors, sometimes referred to as filters that influence the association. Most notable of these filters is the host plant chemistry, environmental conditions as well as microbe-

microbe interactions (Saunders *et al.*, 2010). However, what is not clear is the potential influence of other external factors that are introduced through anthropogenic means linked to technological advancement. One system in which plant-microbe relationship could be impacted is the use of nanomaterials in agro-ecosystem.

Application of Nanoparticles on Plants as Fertilizers:

Applications of nanomaterials are becoming increasingly popular, especially with their usage as Nanofertilizers and nanopesticides for precision and sustainable agriculture. Unfortunately, there is no existing guideline that reflects their potential impacts on plant associated microbes. Hence, this review aims to provide insights about existing literatures on this topic and reflects on potential implication for sustainable agricultural practices.

Integrating cutting-edge nanotechnology into agriculture, including fertiliser creation, is considered one of the greatest feasible methods to significantly increase crop yield and sustain the world's constantly growing population (Lal, R.2008).The application of nanoparticles in agriculture as fertilizers is attributed to their improved characterization, absorption and responsiveness, as well as surface and adhesion effects (Chhipa,H.2017).

Nanofertilizers are macro or micronutrient fertilizers that are used to increase agricultural yields and have a particle size of less than 100 nm. Nanofertilizers are nanomaterials responsible for providing one or more types of nutrients to growing plants, supporting their growth and improving production (Chhipa, H. 2017).They are presented in two different types. On one hand, the nanomaterials supply nutrients to plants to improve their development and yield,

on the other, they are the carriers of nutrients and only assist in the transport and release of nutrients without directly being used as a nutrient source (Liu, R.; 2015).

Nanoparticles' Adverse Effects:

Biosynthesized nanoparticles offer enormous potential to alleviate stress, boost growth and improve agricultural production. However, the unintentional release of some nanoparticles into the environment poses a threat to both aquatic and land plants (Ranjan et al. 2021). For instance, in their study, (Tarrahi et al. 2019) reported the adverse effect of CdSe nanoparticles on the morphology and peroxidase enzyme of common Duckweed (*Lemna minor*), with it having an increased concentration of superoxide dismutase enzyme, catalase, phenols and flavonoids, in contrast with the results of (Movafeghi et al. 2019).

Furthermore, Zn, Se nanoparticles have been found to have a certain toxic effect on the growth of *Lemna minor* by triggering the plants' defence system due to phytotoxicity (Tarrahi et al. 2018). Furthermore, carbon nanotubes were found to trigger oxidative stress in red spinach. Hence, it is crucial to mention that the toxicity of nanoparticles depends on the method used for their production. Several studies have shown that plant-mediated nanoparticles present less to no eco-toxicity towards plants in general and aquatic plants in particular (Plachtová et al. 2018). However, further investigations should be carried out to ascertain the effect of nanoparticles synthesized using plant species on aquatic plants.

Conclusions:

To maximize yields and all eviate poverty and malnutrition, nanoparticles have been recognized as highly beneficial for plant biomass production and enhancement of crop nutritional

quality. This review highlighted the attributes of biosynthesized nanomaterials as sustainable alternatives to conventional chemical fertilizers.

These potential agroinputs can be readily absorbed by plants and are environmentally friendly crop nutrient supplements (Ca, Mg and Fe NPs), with advantages beyond fertilization. Thus, the review also highlighted the use of nanoparticles such as Ti, Ag and Zn, which can be integrated into cropping systems to enhance the plant's defence mechanism against disease attack. However, fewer studies have investigated the broad application of nanoparticles in pest and disease management, offering an opportunity for future research in crop protection.

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